

COMPARISON STUDY OF LATERAL LOAD RESISTING SYSTEMS OF MULTI STORIED BUILDING BY CONSIDERING HIGH SEISMIC ZONE

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ABSTRACT:

We all know that earthquakes may cause disasters from ancient times. These days, buildings are thinner and more prone to swaying, making them more hazardous during earthquakes. Engineers and researchers have already found ways to make the buildings more resistant to earthquakes.

Use of lateral load resisting devices inside the building arrangement has greatly enhanced the structure's performance in earthquakes, according to many reasonable research. We have used a 15Mx12m design in our current study. the work has been applied for the different instances exploitation spur walls, bracings, and dampers for the various heights, using the software programme ETABS 9.7.4. The present analysis considers a maximum height of 33.3 metres.

INTRODUCTION:

Base shear, lateral displacements, and lateral drifts are some of the seismic characteristics that have been modelled and examined. According to IS 1893-2002, the research was conducted on Zone V and medium soil types.

A clean frame, bracings, shear walls, dampers, lateral load resisting systems, response spectrum method, drifts, time period, base shear, seismic zone, and soft soil are all terms that may be used to describe this kind of structure.

Devastating towns and villages have been levelled on almost every continent by earthquakes, making them one of the biggest threats to life on Earth. Because large earthquakes may cause the near-instantaneous collapse of buildings and other structures, they are among the most terrifying natural disasters that humans dread. Also, practically all of the damage that earthquakes do is to buildings that humans have built. Damage to man-made infrastructure including buildings, dams, bridges, and landslides is another way earthquakes kill people. The complexity of earthquake engineering is exacerbated by the fact that many earthquakes provide little to no warning before they happen.

When it comes to earthquake design, some of the biggest issues stem from the architect's initial idea choice. If a building is poorly designed, no amount of engineering can make it earthquake proof. Building form is critical to how they react, as seen by the damages that have happened during earthquake disasters. Simplicity, regularity, and symmetry in elevation and plan are the ideal features of a building form. The uniform and predictable distribution of forces in a structure is enhanced by these qualities, whereas any abnormalities are likely to result in

to a more robust dynamic reaction, in certain areas of the building anyhow. Also, buildings with a large plan area may not behave as expected due to variations in ground behaviour, which are not always predictable. This causes different parts of the building to be shaken differently, creating obvious problems.

On the other hand, buildings with a high ratio of plan area to height will generate high overturning moments. Given the peculiarities of the building's design, torsional from ground motion may pose a significant threat. To illustrate the point, it is necessary to account for torsional moment along a vertical axis when designing for situations where the centre of gravity and the centre of resistance are not in the same location. We can identify three practical and effective ways for achieving appropriate seismic response of a structure. The three main ones are mechanical devices for structural control, isolation, and energy absorption at plastic hinges.

DAMPERS

EnergyDissipationSystem(Dampers)

Mechanics that channel the force of an earthquake into certain tools that may bend or break under the strain. They lessen the amount of seismic stress on a building by increasing energy dissipation in that building. The structure does not rely on them. Dampers absorb some of the seismic energy that passes through them, reducing the building's tremors. Actions by When seismic waves from the earth begin to infiltrate a building's foundation and cause the base to move, the presence or absence of dampers in the structure makes a difference. The structure will not move from its current location because of inertia.

SHEARWALL

To transmit lateral stresses from outside walls, floors and roofs to the ground foundation in a direction parallel to their planes, a building's foundation may be reinforced with a shear wall, which is a stiff vertical diaphragm. The vertical truss and reinforced-concrete walls are two such examples. Torsional forces are very strong because they combine the lateral forces produced by wind, earthquakes, and uneven settlement loads with the weight of the building and its inhabitants. A structure may be sheared to pieces by these forces. A stiff wall, either attached to the outside of the frame or placed within it, may be used to reinforce it and keep it from rotating at the joints. Having shear walls is crucial for tall structures that are vulnerable to seismic and lateral wind impacts.

BRACINGS

Braced frames develop their resistance to lateral forces by the bracing action of diagonal members. The braces induce forces in the associated beams and columns so that all work together like a truss with all members subjected to stresses that are primarily axial.

BRACED STRUCTURE LITERATUREREVIEW

AbhijeetBaikerikar,KanchanKanagali

We know that earthquakes cause disasters from ancient times. Modern buildings are more fragile due to their increased slenderness and susceptibility to swaying during earthquakes. In the past, engineers and researchers have sought to make the buildings as earthquake resistant as possible. The use of lateral load resisting technologies into building layouts has been shown to significantly enhance seismic performance in several empirical investigations. For this study, we employed ETABS 9.7.0, a square grid with dimensions of 20 m x 5 m bays in all directions, and we tested various shear wall and bracing configurations at varying heights, with a maximum height of 75 m taken into account. Seismic factors such as base shear, lateral displacements, and lateral drifts are modelled to investigate the impact of various situations and heights.

Zone V and all soil types described in IS 1893-2002 have been thoroughly studied. Increases in both lateral displacements and drift are proportional to the building's height. Case 1 (Bare Frame) results in the largest lateral displacements and drifts when compared to the other examples. After shear walls and bracings are inserted into the bare frame, lateral displacements and drift are considerably reduced. The preceding research provides essential information, one of which is that base shear, lateral displacements, and lateral drifts rise dramatically as soil texture changes from hard to soft. Soft dirt requires extra caution. Because the time period is proportionate to the mass, the time period required to complete a building's tasks grows in direct proportion to the building's height. Case 2 (Shear Wall in the Middle) stands out as the most efficient and effective from the research. With increasing time, base shear is reduced. The installation of shear walls and bracings drastically reduces the time period.

A.K. Shaik Vinod Hosur and Mohammed Azam

Because of its enhanced lateral stiffness and strength, the dual structural system made up of a concrete shear wall and a special moment resistant frame (SMRF) performs better during seismic events. A building's seismic performance is greatly enhanced by a well-designed system of shear walls inside its frame. We evaluate the seismic performance of various configurations of RC moment resistant framed building structures with varied shear wall arrangements to determine the optimal structural framing system for improved seismic resistance. By positioning shear walls in various ways inside the structural framework, we may evaluate how the structure performs in terms of stiffness, damping characteristics, and strength. In order to assess seismic performance, analytical techniques such as response spectra and nonlinear static pushover are used. The research found that for improved seismic performance, shear walls should be provided symmetrically in the building's outermost moment resistant frames and ideally coupled in mutually perpendicular directions to create a core.

Abhijeet Baikerikar, Kanchan Kanagali

From the ancient time we know earthquake is a disaster causing event. Recent days structures are becoming more and more slender and more susceptible to sway and hence dangerous in the earthquake. Researchers and engineers have worked out in the past to make the structures as earthquake resistant. After many practical studies it has shown that use of lateral load resisting systems in the building configuration has tremendously improved

the performance of the structure in earthquake. In present research we have used square grid of 20m in each direction of 5m bay in each direction, software used is ETABS 9.7.0, the work has been carried out for the different cases using shear wall and bracings for the different heights, maximum height considered for the present study is 75m. The modeling is done to examine the effect of different cases along with different heights on seismic parameters like base shear, lateral displacements and lateral drifts. The study has been carried out for the Zone V and all types of soils as specified in IS 1893-2002. Keywords: Bare Frame, Bracings, Shear Walls, Lateral Load Resisting Systems, Response Spectrum Method, Lateral Displacements, Drifts, Time Period, Base Shear, Seismic Zone, Soft soil.

SHEARWALLBRACINGSANDDAMPERS SHEAR WALLS

Any vertical structural part that can withstand the combined shear, moment, and axial loads imposed by gravity and lateral loads is considered to be a shear wall. Typically, multi-story buildings are required to have reinforced concrete walls, which might incorporate lift wells or shear walls. The best design for a structure has its centroid and mass centre coincide. Because a shear wall's primary role is to improve stiffness for lateral load resistance, its installation is an effective way to strengthen a building's structural structure. As seen in figure, shear walls are often used as a vertical structural component in contemporary skyscrapers to withstand the lateral stresses that may be generated by natural disasters like earthquakes and wind. Shear walls may have a variety of cross sections, from the more common rectangular to more unusual ones like cannel, T, L, barbell, box, etc. Cores hold and carry utilities like lifts, whereas walls aid to enclose spaces. Windows on outside walls, doors or hallways in interior walls, or lift cores will always need the cutting of holes in the wall. From an architectural and practical perspective, opening size and placement may differ.

Shear wall construction has recently become more common for usage in high-rise buildings, particularly those housing service apartments or serving as office or commercial towers. The system's efficiency as a structural system for 30-35 story buildings has been shown (MARSONO & SUBEDI, 2000). During the last 30 years of record keeping, no tall structure with a shear wall feature has fallen due to earthquakes or severe winds (FINTEL, 1995).

DAMPERS

In seismic structures upgrading, one of the lateral force reduction caused by the earthquake is use of dampers. During an earthquake, high energy is applied to the structure. This energy is applied in two types of kinetic and potential (strain) to structure and it is absorbed or amortized. If structure is free of damping, its vibration will be continuously, but due to the material damping, vibration is reduced. Input energy caused by earthquake to structure is presented in the following equation:

$$E = E_k + E_s + E_n + E_d(1)$$

In this equation, E is earthquake input energy, E_k is kinetic energy, E_s is reversible strain energy in the

is the elastic range, E_h is the quantity of energy lost as a result of inelastic deformation, and E_d is the quantity of energy amortised by the extra damper. They have a designated spot in seismic isolation systems that make use of energy dissipation technologies. The flow of a soft metal, the friction between two metals, the motion of a piston inside a slimy substance, or the viscoelastic behaviour of materials like rubber-like substances are all potential strategies for enhancing damping. Modulation of Structural Reaction via Damping Increasing the amount of damping decreases the structural response, which includes acceleration and displacement. The influence of damping is insignificant on the spectrum amount at low frequencies (near zero) and on response acceleration at high frequencies. The frequency range of 0.3 to 2.5 seconds is where the damping effect is most noticeable, as seen in Figures 1 and 2.

TYPES OF DAMPERS

Different types of dampers are defined by their characteristics and how they work: frictional, metal-flowing, viscous, viscoelastic, shape memory alloy (SMA), and mass. Dampers have several benefits,

including a high energy absorption rate, ease of installation and replacement, and synchronisation with other structural parts. in the year 2006, according to the journal.

FrictionDampers

In this type of damper, seismic energy is spent in overcoming friction in the contact surfaces. Among other features of these dampers can be classified as avoiding fatigue in served loads (due to the non-active dampers under load) and their performance independent to loading velocity and ambient temperature. These dampers are installed in parallelto bracing (journal, 2006).

The effect of using friction dampers on structure capacity curve

Rotational friction dampers are shown. Because

and make, this type of damper is converted to one the most common types of friction dampers.

(Warn, 2004) Using rotational friction dampers in retrofitting.

BRACINGS

Any building that is likely to experience lateral stresses should have a braced frame installed. A bracing frame strengthens a building to withstand lateral forces like earthquake and wind. Members of a braced frame are often constructed from structural steel, a material that performs well in both compression and tension.

The bracing system distributes the lateral stresses, while the frame's beams and columns take up the vertical loads. In addition to lowering lateral displacement and column bending moments, braced frames are cost-effective, simple to construct, and provide the necessary design freedom to achieve the necessary stiffness and strength.

Story	Drift Y in General Building	Drift(X) Using Bracings	Drift(X) using Dampers	Drift(X) Using Shear walls
STORY11	0.000311	0.000317	0.000337	0.000803
STORY10	0.000893	0.000814	0.000844	0.000879
STORY9	0.000889	0.000896	0.000722	0.000743
STORY8	0.001026	0.000783	0.000783	0.000807
STORY7	0.001163	0.000826	0.000845	0.000837
STORY6	0.00123	0.000867	0.000833	0.000839
STORY5	0.001379	0.000888	0.000912	0.000895
STORY4	0.001439	0.000884	0.000899	0.000863
STORY3	0.001517	0.00085	0.00086	0.000799
STORY2	0.001522	0.000786	0.00081	0.000676
STORY1	0.001126	0.000392	0.000392	0.000439

But, bracing, depending on their placement, may be a pain since they muck with façade designs and opening placements. In response, bracing has become an integral part of the design of many modernist and high-tech structures.

Support structures

Two bracing mechanisms give the necessary resistance to horizontal forces:

Bracing that runs vertically

The transmission of horizontal forces to ground level is accomplished by load channels provided by bracing between column lines in vertical planes. A minimum of three vertical bracing planes were necessary for framed structures to withstand torsion around a vertical axis and brace in both planar and transverse directions.

Supporting horizontally

Loads may be transferred from the horizontal planes to the vertical bracing planes via the load routes provided by the bracing at each floor level. Although the floor system could provide enough resistance, horizontal bracing is required at every level. Bracing may be necessary for roofs. **RESULTS AND ANALYSIS**

DRIFT IN X DIRECTION

Story	Drift X in General Building	Drift(X) Using Bracings	Drift(X) using Dampers	Drift(X) Using Shear walls
STORY11	0.000433	0.000362	0.000382	0.00041
STORY10	0.000613	0.000431	0.000451	0.000433
STORY9	0.000783	0.000483	0.000483	0.000489
STORY8	0.000944	0.000337	0.000347	0.00032
STORY7	0.001082	0.000376	0.000386	0.000343
STORY6	0.001201	0.000803	0.000833	0.000354
STORY5	0.001304	0.000616	0.000636	0.000351
STORY4	0.00139	0.000814	0.000834	0.000329
STORY3	0.001456	0.000394	0.00061	0.000483
STORY2	0.001474	0.000337	0.000377	0.000413
STORY1	0.00111	0.000446	0.000446	0.000288

DRIFT IN Y DIRECTION

STORY SHEAR

Story	Force VX in general building	Force VX for Bracing systems	Force VX in Dampers	Force VX in Shear wall
STORY11	-657.37	-731.52	-751.52	-920.88
STORY10	-1320.13	-1475.35	-1675.35	-1873.6
STORY9	-1917.44	-2158.46	-2188.46	-2755.95
STORY8	-2458.1	-2729.27	-2769.27	-3517.29
STORY7	-2942.95	-3256.18	-3276.18	-4227.1
STORY6	-3384.8	-3727.81	-3787.81	-4874.77
STORY5	-3788.47	-4151.95	-4161.95	-5469.71
STORY4	-4180.78	-4537.81	-4577.81	-6021.35
STORY3	-4508.34	-4895.01	-5112.01	-6539.09
STORY2	-4838.38	-5228.55	-5228.55	-7032.35
STORY1	-5137.78	-5548.73	-5548.73	-7528.42

Story	Moment MY in General Buildings	Moment MY for Bracings	Moment MY for Dampers	Moment MY for Shear walls
STORY11	-1972.12	-2194.56	-2194.56	-2528.4
STORY10	-3952.52	-6620.6	-6620.6	-7910.95
STORY9	-11884.8	-13036	-13036	-15882.5
STORY8	-19053.1	-21223.8	-21223.8	-26198.1
STORY7	-27882	-30992.3	-30992.3	-38843.2
STORY6	-38036.4	-42175.2	-42175.2	-53051.2
STORY5	-49401.8	-54831	-54831	-69204.1
STORY4	-61884.2	-68243.8	-68243.8	-87051.9
STORY3	-75409.8	-82922.9	-82922.9	-108413
STORY2	-89925.5	-98602.5	-98602.5	-127274
STORY1	-106946	-116907	-116907	-151825

Story	Point	Load	GENERAL BUILDING FORCE IN X DIRECTION (FX)	BRACINGS FORCE IN X DIRECTION (FX)	DAMPERS FORCE IN X DIRECTION (FX)	SHEAR WALLS FORCE IN X DIRECTION (FX)
BASE	1	EQX	-144.95	-68.21	-68.21	-43.27
BASE	1	EQY	0	1.54	1.54	1.9
BASE	2	EQX	-185.36	-81.03	-81.03	-85.36
BASE	2	EQY	0	7.17	7.17	-950.18
BASE	3	EQX	-185.36	-80.24	-80.24	0
BASE	3	EQY	0	0	0	-1071.97

Story	Building twist T in General Building	Building twist T by using Bracings	Building twist T by using Dampers	Building twist T by using Shear walls
STORY11	3944.245	4389.112	4389.112	5525.297
STORY10	7920.79	8852.077	8852.077	11241.6
STORY9	11504.81	12850.77	12850.77	16415.59
STORY8	14738.82	16375.83	16375.83	21105.77
STORY7	17657.72	19537.1	19537.1	25362.61
STORY6	20308.83	22365.84	22365.84	29248.62
STORY5	22750.85	24911.88	24911.88	32818.28
STORY4	24964.88	27225.87	27225.87	36128.08
STORY3	27051.25	29358.06	29358.06	39234.52
STORY2	29051.45	31359.3	31359.3	42194.08
STORY1	30946.88	33280.39	33280.39	45138.33

SUPPORT REACTIONS

Story	Point	Load	GENERAL BUILDING FORCE IN Y DIRECTION	BRACINGS FORCE IN Y DIRECTION	DAMPERS FORCE IN Y DIRECTION	SHEAR WALLS FORCE IN Y DIRECTION
BASE	1	EQX	0	1.23	1.23	2.06
BASE	1	EQY	-145.51	-84.83	-84.83	-62.57
BASE	2	EQX	0	-58.3	-58.3	-63.36
BASE	2	EQY	-145.51	-549.47	-549.47	-950.18
BASE	3	EQX	0	0	0	0
BASE	3	EQY	-145.51	-604	-604	-1071.97

Story	Point	Load	GENERAL BUILDING FORCE IN Z DIRECTION	BRACINGS FORCE IN Z DIRECTION	DAMPERS FORCE IN Z DIRECTION	SHEAR WALLS FORCE IN Z DIRECTION
BASE	1	EQX	-1143.71	-911.99	-911.99	-894.37
BASE	1	EQY	1207.98	-1160.98	-1160.98	-1213.04
BASE	2	EQX	-213.7	-723.35	-723.35	-782.5
BASE	2	EQY	1207.98	-2544.33	-2544.33	-4379.88
BASE	3	EQX	-49.17	-770.37	-770.37	-1072.09
BASE	3	EQY	1207.98	0	0	0

CONCLUSIONS

The following are the conclusions:

1. The drifts or displacements of building with shear walls are less with comparison of Bracings and Dampers and general Building

The general building exhibits the most significant displacements and drifts when compared to the bracing, shear wall and dampers situations.

3. The analysis clearly shows that shear wall construction is the most efficient and effective method.
4. Out of all the situations (general, bracing, shear wall, and dampers), the story shear for forces (V) and moment (M) is highest for the structure that uses shear walls.
5. In comparison to other situations, the shear wall scenario likewise has the largest value of building twist (T).

6. From tale 11 to story 1 (top to bottom story), the narrative shear values always rise.
7. The shear wall examples had lower values for the support responses compared to the other cases in the research.

Shear wall systems are the most cost-effective of the bunch, and in areas with higher seismic intensities, a combination of shear walls and dampers is the way to go.

SCOPE FOR FURTHER WORK

The research may be expanded to account for varying building design sizes by comparing the findings of systems located at different places.

- Additional research may be conducted by using other methods and for varying heights.

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